
Perception of Edutainment Broadcasting on Youth Reproductive Health Decision in Benin Metropolis

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Abstract

The researchers examined the impact of edutainment broadcasting on youth reproductive health decision-making in Benin metropolis. The objectives were to find out the perceptions of Benin youth regarding the role of media in shaping reproductive health knowledge and behaviours, evaluate the effectiveness of edutainment broadcasting in enhancing knowledge of reproductive health among youth and identify the barriers to accessing reproductive health information among youth. The health belief model was used as the theoretical framework. A survey research design was adopted, with a sample size of 383 respondents selected through random sampling. The findings revealed that media, including edutainment broadcasting, play a significant role in shaping youth reproductive health knowledge and behaviours and that edutainment broadcasting is perceived as an effective tool for enhancing reproductive health knowledge among Benin youth. However, significant barriers to accessing reproductive health information, including financial constraints, stigma and cultural or religious restrictions, were also identified. The researchers concluded that edutainment broadcasting has the potential to play a significant role in promoting reproductive health awareness and education among Benin youth, but that significant barriers must be addressed. Recommendations were made for policymakers, healthcare providers and media practitioners to develop and implement policies, services and programmes that support reproductive health education and awareness among youth.

Keywords: Edutainment Broadcasting, Reproductive Health, Youth, Health Model, Benin Metropolis

Introduction

Broadcasting serves as a fundamental medium for communication, playing a crucial role in disseminating information across diverse audiences. It encompasses various forms of media, including television, radio and digital platforms, which collectively inform, educate and entertain the public. In recent years, the broadcasting landscape has evolved significantly, giving rise to innovative formats that merge entertainment with educational